

SAMPLING TO ESTIMATE THE AVERAGE NUMBER OF BUNCHES PER VINE

TABLE OF CONFIDENCE INTERVALS FOR ESTIMATION ERRORS

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This document is an appendix to the technical review "How to better estimate bunch number at field level?" published in IVES Technical Reviews, vine and wine.

How to read this document?

The following pages present 5 tables to obtain the confidence interval bounds for the average number of bunches per vine with confidence levels of 99%, 95%, 90%, 75%, and 50%.

These tables can be read using two sample properties:

- The sample size that correspond to the number of vines that have been observed;
- The Coefficient of Variation (CV) of the sample computed from its standard deviation and its mean.

These two values should be reported in the tables using the columns for the sample size and the rows for the CV. The estimation error associated with the sample will then have a 99%, 95%, 90%, 75%, and 50% chance of being lower than the obtained value, depending on the chosen table.

Boundary of the 99% confidence interval (estimation error as a percentage)

CV	Sample size																							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	12	14	16	18	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	60	70	80	90	100
0.75	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	82.7	71.5	59	50.5	45.8	40.8	37.4	34.3	28.7	26.5	24.7	22.8	21.3
0.725	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	86.1	73.5	68.3	56.2	47.9	43.7	37.9	34.4	32.5	28.2	26.6	23.9	22.6	20.6
0.7	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	98.5	84.7	73.7	69.1	52.6	46.1	39.9	38.3	35.1	30.8	27	24.8	23.2	21.1	19.9
0.675	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	87.2	79.3	68.8	62.6	52.7	42.4	38.5	34.8	32.5	30.2	25.7	23	22.2	20.1	18.6
0.65	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	85	71.7	64.3	58	47	41.6	37.9	32.5	30.2	28.7	25	22.3	20.8	18.7	18.3
0.625	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	97.8	78.8	66.7	61.2	54	44.2	37.7	36.3	31.3	29	26.9	24.4	22.1	19.8	18.7	17.6
0.6	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	93.9	75.9	64.1	54.5	50.4	42.5	34.8	32.1	29.2	27.2	26.1	22.9	21.1	19.1	17.9	16.6
0.575	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	82.3	64.9	61.3	51.7	46.9	40.9	34.7	31.2	28.8	25.6	24.5	21.5	19.4	18	17	15.7
0.55	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	92.7	76.4	66.2	58.5	50	43.9	37.2	32.3	30.1	27.7	24.4	23.5	20.6	18.5	17.1	16.3	14.5
0.525	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	93.6	85.8	68.5	56.9	52	46.3	44.5	35.6	31.2	27.7	25.7	23.7	21.9	19.5	17.9	16.6	15.5	14.4
0.5	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	91.5	79.3	70.2	56.2	48.3	42.4	38.8	32.7	29	25.3	24.5	21.8	20.6	17.6	16.6	15.1	14.3	13.3
0.475	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	87.8	70.1	61	52.1	46.1	40.4	36.9	30	27	24	21.7	21.3	19.5	17.2	16	14.6	13.9	12.9
0.45	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	86.5	74.1	66.1	54.6	47.4	41.7	38.4	34.8	30.3	25.8	22.9	20.5	19.4	19	16.1	14.7	13.7	13	12.4
0.425	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	85	69.1	61.6	51.3	40.9	39.1	34.2	31	27.1	23.8	20.8	19.1	18.5	17	15.3	14.3	12.9	12.1	11.2
0.4	>100	>100	>100	>100	91.4	72.7	66.1	57.4	46.3	39.7	34.5	33.1	29.7	25.1	22.1	19.2	17.9	17.2	16	14.4	13	12	11.3	10.8
0.375	>100	>100	>100	96.6	77.4	64.3	58.7	55.1	39.9	34.3	33	29.6	27.1	23.7	20.7	18.5	16.9	15.5	14.9	13.2	12.5	11.5	10.6	9.9
0.35	>100	>100	>100	95.1	76.5	59.3	51.3	43.2	38.8	33.5	29.8	28.7	24.6	21.1	18.7	17.4	15.6	14.5	13.7	12.5	11.1	10.7	10	9.4
0.325	>100	>100	>100	73.3	66.6	53.4	47.5	42.2	33.9	29	27.4	24	23.3	19.9	18.4	15.6	14.4	13.3	12.7	11.1	10.4	9.7	9.2	8.5
0.3	>100	>100	>100	72.7	54.5	49.6	40.7	37.5	31.8	28.9	24.2	22.1	20.5	18.5	15.7	14	13.1	12.3	11.5	10.7	9.6	8.9	8.7	7.8
0.275	>100	>100	83.8	59	47	40.3	38.5	32.2	28.3	23.8	21.7	19.6	17.9	16	14.3	12.9	12.2	11.3	10.8	9.4	8.6	8.1	7.8	7.2
0.25	>100	>100	73.9	52.4	42.2	36.8	31.7	28.6	24.9	22	19.5	18.4	16.9	15	12.9	11.9	11.2	9.9	9.7	8.8	7.9	7.5	7	6.7
0.225	>100	94.2	56.6	46	37	30	27.9	25.5	22.2	19	17.5	16.1	14.9	12.7	11.8	10.7	10	9.2	8.6	7.9	7.3	6.8	6.4	6
0.2	>100	78.5	50	40.6	31.5	27.7	24.1	21.8	19.5	16.4	15.9	14.2	13.4	11.6	10.1	9.5	8.4	8	7.8	7	6.3	5.8	5.5	5.3
0.175	>100	63.2	41.7	31.4	27	23	20.6	19	15.9	15	13.3	12.9	11.2	10.2	9	8.5	7.5	7.1	6.7	6.1	5.5	5.1	4.9	4.7
0.15	>100	53.9	34	26.2	22.6	19.3	18.4	15.9	13.7	12	11.3	10.4	9.8	8.6	7.6	7.2	6.5	6.2	5.6	5.4	4.7	4.4	4.2	4
0.125	74.5	40.7	26.7	23.2	17.7	16.2	14.5	13.2	11.4	10.4	9.5	8.6	8	7.2	6.4	5.8	5.4	5.1	4.7	4.3	4	3.6	3.4	3.3
0.1	60.1	32.2	22.8	17.7	15	13.4	11.5	10.2	8.9	8.5	7.3	6.9	6.4	5.6	5.1	4.6	4.3	4	3.9	3.4	3.2	2.9	2.7	2.6
0.075	38.5	23	16.6	12.8	11	9.3	8.6	7.7	6.8	6.1	5.6	5.1	4.8	4.3	3.8	3.5	3.2	3	2.8	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.1	2
0.05	27.2	14.5	10.4	8.3	6.8	6.2	5.7	5.1	4.4	4	3.7	3.4	3.2	2.8	2.5	2.3	2.1	2	1.9	1.7	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3
0.025	13.7	7.1	5.1	4	3.4	3.2	2.7	2.6	2.2	2	1.9	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.1	1	1	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7
0.01	4.9	2.9	2.1	1.6	1.4	1.3	1.2	1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3

Boundary of the 95% confidence interval (estimation error as a percentage)

CV	Sample size																							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	12	14	16	18	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	60	70	80	90	100
0.75	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	91.1	81.7	76.4	65.6	53.2	48.9	42.2	40.1	33.8	30.7	27.8	25.8	23.6	22.2	19.5	18.5	16.9	16	15.4
0.725	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	89.5	77.6	70.2	59.9	52	45.5	42.1	39.6	32.9	29.3	26.7	24.5	22.9	21.6	19.5	18	16.7	15.6	14.4
0.7	>100	>100	>100	>100	94.7	92.3	74.4	68.7	57.1	47.4	44.8	40.2	36.4	32.6	27.5	25.6	23.8	22.5	20.4	18.5	17.1	16	15.3	14.3
0.675	>100	>100	>100	>100	94.5	80.9	73	62.6	55	47.5	41.3	37.1	35.5	30.8	26.9	24.5	22.3	21.6	20.1	18	16.4	15.5	14.1	13.5
0.65	>100	>100	>100	>100	83.2	78.1	67.4	58.7	51.6	45.3	40.6	36.4	33.3	28.9	25.6	24	21.7	20	19.2	17	16.1	14.9	13.5	13.1
0.625	>100	>100	>100	95.5	81.7	69.5	65.1	57.7	48.7	40.8	38.3	36.4	32	27	24.6	22.6	21.1	19.6	18.3	16.9	15.1	14.2	13	12.7
0.6	>100	>100	>100	90	72.9	66.5	59.5	52.8	46.3	39.5	36.1	32.2	29.5	26.6	23.3	21.5	19.8	18.1	17.5	15.9	14.8	13.7	12.8	12
0.575	>100	>100	>100	83.9	68.6	62.6	55.8	51.1	42	36.2	34.9	31.5	28.6	25.1	22.5	20.7	19.1	18	17.1	15.1	13.8	12.9	12.2	11.3
0.55	>100	>100	95.7	75.3	66.8	59.5	52.3	46.4	40.3	36.1	33.3	30	26.9	23.3	21.5	20	18.1	17.1	16	14.4	13.3	12.3	11.7	10.8
0.525	>100	>100	90.4	73.8	61.4	55.5	48.5	42.1	37.2	33.8	30.8	28.3	26.4	22.5	20.2	18.1	17.5	16.2	15.1	14	12.8	11.8	11.1	10.6
0.5	>100	>100	81.9	68.7	58.3	50.2	44.3	42.4	36.2	31.4	29.6	26.8	24.5	21.3	19.3	17.5	16.4	15.3	14.6	12.7	12	11.2	10.5	10
0.475	>100	>100	79	62.6	54.6	48.5	40.3	38.7	34.4	30.5	26.9	25.7	23.7	20.6	18.2	16.9	15.7	14.7	14	12.4	11.4	10.6	10.1	9.5
0.45	>100	87.6	69.9	58	48.6	41.9	39.4	36.4	31.5	27.2	25.8	23.5	22.2	19.7	17.4	16	14.8	13.9	13	11.9	11	10.1	9.5	9.1
0.425	>100	87.3	64.4	52.9	45.7	41	36.1	33.8	29.8	25.9	24	22.2	20.9	18	16.3	14.9	13.7	12.9	12.3	11.1	10.1	9.5	9.1	8.4
0.4	>100	75.7	58.1	49.6	43.1	36.5	33.7	31	27	24.8	21.7	21.1	19.1	17.3	15.4	13.9	13	12.3	11.6	10.6	9.4	8.9	8.4	7.9
0.375	98.2	70.4	55.3	44.8	39	34.8	30.5	29.4	25	22.4	20.7	19.2	17.8	16	14	13	12.1	11.3	10.8	9.7	9	8.3	7.9	7.4
0.35	88.1	65.9	51.3	41.8	35.9	31.7	28.3	25.7	23.3	21.8	19.5	18.4	16.7	14.7	13.1	12.1	11.4	10.6	10.2	9.3	8.3	8	7.3	6.9
0.325	82.6	57.6	47.2	36	33.1	28.8	26.3	24.5	21.4	19	17.7	16.4	15.4	13.7	12.7	11.2	10.5	9.9	9.2	8.4	7.7	7.2	6.8	6.5
0.3	79.5	54.1	42.3	33.9	28.8	27.1	23.6	22.6	19.5	17.9	16.3	15.2	14.2	12.9	11.3	10.3	9.6	9.1	8.5	7.8	7.2	6.6	6.3	5.9
0.275	72.1	47.4	37.2	30	26.6	24.3	21.9	20.3	18.1	16.2	14.8	13.9	13.1	11.5	10.3	9.5	8.8	8.2	7.9	7.1	6.6	6.2	5.8	5.4
0.25	66	43.2	33.5	26.1	24	21.5	19.7	18.3	16.3	15.1	13.5	12.7	12	10.6	9.5	8.7	8.1	7.5	7.1	6.5	5.9	5.6	5.2	5
0.225	58.6	37.4	29.8	25.1	21.6	19.3	17.6	16.4	14.8	13.3	12.2	11.3	10.6	9.4	8.5	7.7	7.2	6.7	6.5	5.9	5.3	5	4.8	4.5
0.2	52.6	32.9	25.8	22.3	19	17.5	15.4	14.8	13	11.7	10.8	10	9.5	8.3	7.5	7	6.4	6	5.7	5.1	4.8	4.4	4.1	3.9
0.175	44.4	28.8	21.4	18.9	16.5	14.7	13.7	12.7	11	10.2	9.6	8.8	8.1	7.2	6.6	6	5.5	5.2	5	4.6	4.2	3.9	3.7	3.5
0.15	38.6	25.5	18.8	15.9	14.1	12.7	11.8	10.9	9.3	8.7	7.9	7.5	7.1	6.2	5.6	5.2	4.8	4.5	4.3	3.9	3.5	3.4	3.2	3
0.125	31.1	19.6	16.2	13.7	11.4	10.5	9.8	8.9	7.9	7.2	6.6	6.1	5.8	5.2	4.7	4.2	4	3.7	3.6	3.2	2.9	2.8	2.6	2.5
0.1	24.3	16.4	12.4	10.5	9.5	8.4	7.8	7.1	6.4	5.8	5.2	4.9	4.7	4.1	3.7	3.5	3.2	3	2.9	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.1	2
0.075	17.8	12	9.4	7.9	7	6.2	5.7	5.4	4.7	4.4	4	3.7	3.5	3.1	2.8	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.1	1.9	1.8	1.7	1.6	1.5
0.05	12.3	8	6.2	5.3	4.6	4.3	3.8	3.6	3.2	2.9	2.6	2.5	2.3	2.1	1.9	1.7	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.1	1	1
0.025	6.1	4	3.1	2.6	2.3	2.1	1.9	1.8	1.6	1.5	1.3	1.2	1.2	1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5
0.01	2.3	1.6	1.2	1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

Boundary of the 90% confidence interval (estimation error as a percentage)

CV	Sample size																							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	12	14	16	18	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	60	70	80	90	100
0.75	>100	>100	86	72.7	64.4	57.7	52.5	49.5	43.3	37.3	34.3	30.6	29.7	26.2	23.7	21.8	20.5	18.9	18.2	16	15.1	14	13.1	12.7
0.725	>100	95.7	82.1	70.2	62.4	56.3	49.5	46.1	41.1	36.7	33.1	31	29.3	25.8	22.6	20.9	19.7	18.3	17.3	16.1	14.8	13.6	12.7	12.1
0.7	>100	95.3	82.3	63.4	59.6	55.7	47.4	44.7	38.4	34.7	32.1	30	28	25	22.3	20.2	19.1	18	16.4	15.1	14	13	12.5	11.8
0.675	>100	89.5	75.7	63.5	57.9	50.5	47.9	42.4	38.1	33.6	30.8	28.2	26.7	23.6	21.2	19.6	18.1	17.1	16.2	14.6	13.5	12.6	11.7	11.3
0.65	97.2	81.9	69.1	60.7	53.5	50.7	44	39.6	36.2	32.6	29.6	27.4	25.7	22.6	20.5	18.8	17.5	16.4	15.5	13.8	13.1	12.3	11.3	10.9
0.625	96.4	77.4	67.6	57.3	51	45.5	42.4	39.4	34.1	30.9	29	27.2	24.7	21.5	19.8	18	16.9	15.8	15	14	12.4	11.6	10.9	10.5
0.6	91.5	78.5	64	55.3	47.2	44.7	40.7	36.2	32.6	29.1	27.5	24.9	23.3	20.7	18.7	17.4	15.8	14.9	14.1	13.2	12.2	11.2	10.6	10.1
0.575	87.9	72.4	61.7	51.3	44.5	42	38.1	34.8	30.2	27.2	26.3	23.9	22.6	20	18.1	16.6	15.5	14.7	13.9	12.4	11.3	10.6	10	9.4
0.55	85.9	68.6	56.5	48.9	44.3	39.9	35.9	34.1	29.3	26.8	25	23.1	21.4	18.9	17.2	16	14.9	14	13.3	11.9	11.1	10.1	9.6	9
0.525	82.2	67.6	53.6	48.9	41.4	37.4	34.4	31.2	28.2	25.5	23.8	22.2	20.9	17.9	16.3	15.1	14.3	13.2	12.5	11.4	10.5	9.8	9.2	8.7
0.5	77.1	62.1	51.2	44.9	39.9	35.1	32.2	30.8	27.3	24.3	22.9	20.9	19.6	17.1	15.5	14.4	13.6	12.5	11.8	10.7	9.9	9.3	8.8	8.3
0.475	72.9	59	48	41.8	37.3	34.3	30.4	28.4	26	23.2	21.5	20	18.8	16.4	14.9	13.8	12.9	12	11.4	10.2	9.6	8.8	8.5	7.9
0.45	73	53.5	45.1	39.1	34.6	30.7	29.1	27	24.1	21.1	20.3	18.6	17.6	15.9	14	13	12	11.5	10.8	9.9	9	8.4	7.9	7.5
0.425	68.5	53.7	41.9	36.4	32.5	29.3	27.3	25.3	22.8	20.6	18.7	17.9	16.9	14.7	13.3	12.2	11.2	10.8	10.1	9.1	8.3	7.9	7.5	7
0.4	65	46.8	39.5	35	31.3	27.6	25.5	23.3	20.7	19.4	17.6	16.8	15.4	14.1	12.6	11.6	10.7	10	9.7	8.8	7.9	7.5	7	6.6
0.375	59.3	44.5	37.5	31.6	28.5	25.7	23.5	22.3	19.7	18	16.7	15.4	14.4	13	11.7	10.8	10	9.3	9.1	8.1	7.5	7	6.6	6.2
0.35	55.9	42.6	35.1	30.2	26.8	24.2	21.8	20.3	18.2	17	15.6	14.5	13.7	11.9	10.9	10	9.5	8.8	8.4	7.7	7	6.6	6	5.8
0.325	51.3	38.2	33.1	27	25.2	21.8	20.5	19.2	16.8	15.5	14.3	13.4	12.5	11.2	10.3	9.3	8.8	8.1	7.7	7	6.4	6.1	5.7	5.4
0.3	49.5	36	29.4	25.1	22.1	20.6	18.7	17.7	15.7	14.4	13.1	12.4	11.5	10.6	9.3	8.6	8	7.5	7.1	6.5	6	5.5	5.3	5
0.275	45.8	32.1	27.3	23.1	20.3	18.8	17.1	16	14.5	13.2	12.1	11.3	10.7	9.4	8.6	7.9	7.3	6.9	6.6	6	5.5	5.2	4.8	4.6
0.25	42.8	30.6	24.6	20.3	18.5	17	15.6	14.6	13.1	12.1	11.1	10.4	9.8	8.7	7.8	7.1	6.7	6.2	5.9	5.4	4.9	4.6	4.4	4.2
0.225	37	26.5	21.6	19	16.5	15	14	13	11.9	10.6	10	9.3	8.8	7.8	7	6.4	6	5.6	5.4	4.9	4.4	4.1	3.9	3.8
0.2	34	23.7	19.2	16.8	14.8	13.9	12.4	11.8	10.5	9.5	8.8	8.1	7.7	6.9	6.2	5.8	5.4	5	4.7	4.3	4	3.7	3.4	3.3
0.175	29.3	20.4	16.3	14.6	12.9	11.7	10.8	10.3	9.1	8.3	7.8	7.2	6.7	6	5.4	5	4.6	4.3	4.2	3.8	3.5	3.2	3.1	2.9
0.15	25.4	18.3	14.1	12.4	11	10	9.4	8.9	7.8	7.2	6.5	6.2	5.8	5.1	4.7	4.3	4	3.8	3.6	3.3	2.9	2.8	2.7	2.5
0.125	21.2	14.5	12	10.6	9.1	8.5	7.8	7.1	6.4	5.9	5.4	5.1	4.8	4.3	3.9	3.5	3.3	3.1	3	2.7	2.5	2.3	2.2	2.1
0.1	16.3	11.8	9.4	8.2	7.5	6.7	6.3	5.7	5.2	4.7	4.3	4.1	3.9	3.5	3.1	2.9	2.7	2.5	2.4	2.2	2	1.8	1.7	1.7
0.075	12.1	8.8	7.3	6.2	5.5	5.1	4.6	4.3	3.9	3.6	3.3	3.1	2.9	2.5	2.4	2.2	2	1.9	1.8	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.2
0.05	8.4	5.8	4.8	4.2	3.7	3.4	3.1	2.9	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.1	1.9	1.7	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.1	1	0.9	0.9	0.8
0.025	4.2	3	2.3	2	1.8	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.1	1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4
0.01	1.7	1.2	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

Boundary of the 75% confidence interval (estimation error as a percentage)

CV	Sample size																							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	12	14	16	18	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	60	70	80	90	100
0.75	51.1	45.2	41.2	37.1	34.2	31.9	30.1	28.7	25.9	23.4	22.1	20.3	19.2	17.3	15.8	14.6	13.8	12.8	12.2	11.1	10.3	9.7	9.1	8.6
0.725	50.8	44.8	39.6	36.2	33	31.4	29	27.1	25.1	23	21	20.1	19	17	15.2	14.1	13.4	12.5	12	10.8	10.1	9.4	8.8	8.3
0.7	50.8	43.8	39.8	34.9	32.5	31.1	28.1	26.7	24.1	22	20.6	19.7	18.2	16.7	15	13.7	12.9	12.2	11.4	10.5	9.7	8.9	8.5	8.1
0.675	49	42.9	37.9	33.9	31.4	29.4	27.7	25.2	23.3	21.1	19.9	18.6	17.7	15.9	14.3	13.1	12.5	11.7	11	10.1	9.4	8.7	8.1	7.8
0.65	47.8	41.6	36.1	32.7	30.5	28.4	26.4	24.6	22.5	20.9	19.1	18	17.1	14.9	13.8	12.7	12	11.2	10.6	9.8	9	8.5	7.8	7.4
0.625	47.1	39.5	35.1	31.9	29.3	27.1	25.7	23.6	21.5	19.8	18.6	17.6	16.4	14.6	13.3	12.1	11.5	10.9	10.3	9.5	8.7	8	7.6	7.2
0.6	45.2	39.1	34.8	30.2	27.9	26.3	24.3	23	20.4	19.2	17.9	16.6	15.6	13.9	12.8	11.9	10.8	10.4	9.8	9.1	8.2	7.8	7.3	6.9
0.575	43.4	37.9	33.2	29.3	26.4	25.1	23.2	21.7	19.6	17.7	17.1	15.8	15	13.6	12.2	11.3	10.5	10.1	9.5	8.4	7.8	7.4	6.9	6.6
0.55	43.6	36.2	31.2	28.2	26	23.9	22.1	21.4	18.8	17.6	16.5	15.4	14.4	12.9	11.7	10.8	10.2	9.6	9.1	8.2	7.7	7.1	6.6	6.3
0.525	41.1	35.2	30.7	27.6	25	23	21.4	20.3	18.1	16.7	15.9	14.7	14.1	12.2	11.1	10.3	9.7	9.2	8.7	7.9	7.2	6.8	6.4	6.1
0.5	40.3	33.5	28.8	26.5	23.9	21.7	20.3	19.7	17.5	15.8	14.8	13.9	13	11.7	10.6	9.8	9.4	8.7	8.1	7.4	6.9	6.5	6.2	5.8
0.475	38.3	32	27	24.6	22.6	21.1	19.1	18.2	16.7	15.4	14.3	13.4	12.5	11.3	10.1	9.4	8.8	8.2	7.9	7.1	6.6	6.1	5.8	5.5
0.45	37.5	30.4	26.3	23.3	21.6	19.4	18.6	17.4	15.7	14.1	13.4	12.5	11.9	10.6	9.6	8.9	8.2	7.7	7.4	6.8	6.1	5.9	5.4	5.2
0.425	35.9	29.4	24.8	22.1	20.4	18.6	17.5	16.5	14.9	13.7	12.7	12	11.3	10.2	9.1	8.3	7.7	7.4	7	6.3	5.9	5.5	5.3	5
0.4	34.2	26.8	23.5	21	19.5	17.5	16.4	15.4	14	12.7	12	11.4	10.6	9.3	8.6	8	7.3	6.9	6.7	6.1	5.5	5.2	4.9	4.6
0.375	31.4	25.3	22.1	19.5	17.9	16.6	15.4	14.6	13	12.1	11	10.5	9.7	8.8	8.1	7.5	6.9	6.5	6.3	5.6	5.2	4.8	4.6	4.3
0.35	29.8	23.8	20.9	18.6	16.8	15.5	14.6	13.7	12.2	11.3	10.4	9.8	9.3	8.2	7.5	6.9	6.5	6.1	5.8	5.3	4.8	4.5	4.2	4
0.325	27.5	22.5	19.9	16.9	15.8	14.2	13.4	12.6	11.2	10.5	9.8	9.1	8.6	7.7	7	6.4	6.1	5.7	5.3	4.9	4.4	4.2	4	3.8
0.3	26.1	21.2	17.9	15.8	14.4	13.2	12.2	11.6	10.6	9.7	8.9	8.4	8	7.1	6.4	5.9	5.5	5.2	4.9	4.5	4.2	3.8	3.7	3.5
0.275	24.3	19	16.5	14.6	13.2	12.2	11.3	10.6	9.5	8.9	8.2	7.7	7.3	6.5	5.9	5.4	5.1	4.7	4.5	4.1	3.8	3.6	3.4	3.2
0.25	23.2	17.8	15.1	13.1	12.1	11.1	10.3	9.6	8.8	8.1	7.5	7.2	6.7	5.9	5.4	5	4.6	4.3	4.1	3.7	3.5	3.2	3	2.9
0.225	20.2	15.7	13.4	12	10.9	9.8	9.3	8.7	8	7.2	6.7	6.3	6	5.4	4.8	4.5	4.2	3.9	3.7	3.3	3.1	2.9	2.7	2.6
0.2	18.5	14	11.8	10.6	9.5	8.9	8.2	7.8	7.1	6.5	5.8	5.6	5.3	4.7	4.3	4	3.7	3.5	3.3	3	2.8	2.6	2.4	2.3
0.175	15.7	12	10.4	9.4	8.4	7.8	7.2	6.7	6.1	5.7	5.3	4.9	4.7	4.1	3.8	3.4	3.2	3	2.9	2.6	2.4	2.3	2.1	2
0.15	13.8	10.7	8.9	7.9	7.2	6.6	6.2	5.9	5.3	4.8	4.4	4.2	4	3.5	3.2	2.9	2.8	2.6	2.5	2.2	2.1	2	1.8	1.7
0.125	11.3	8.8	7.5	6.8	6	5.5	5.1	4.9	4.4	4	3.8	3.4	3.3	3	2.7	2.4	2.3	2.2	2.1	1.9	1.7	1.6	1.5	1.4
0.1	9.1	7.1	5.9	5.3	4.8	4.4	4.2	3.9	3.5	3.2	2.9	2.8	2.7	2.4	2.1	2	1.8	1.8	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.1
0.075	6.7	5.2	4.5	4	3.6	3.4	3.1	2.9	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.1	2	1.8	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.1	1	1	0.9	0.9
0.05	4.5	3.5	3	2.7	2.4	2.2	2	1.9	1.8	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.1	1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.6
0.025	2.3	1.8	1.5	1.3	1.2	1.1	1	1	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
0.01	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1

